

JURISPRUDENCE

THE INTERNATIONAL CRIMINAL COURT AS THE PRINCIPAL ORGAN FOR PUNISHING THE AGGRESSOR STATE AND PREVENTING AGGRESSION

Tamerlan Hajiyev

*The Academy of Public Administration under the
President of the Republic of Azerbaijan*

Abstract

It is known that among the purposes of the United Nations, the primary goal is the maintenance of international peace and security, for the achievement of which States have undertaken to take «effective measures» to prevent and eliminate threats to the world and «suppress aggression» (Article 1 of the Charter of the United Nations), which has gained «special popularity» over the past half century. Of course, one of such «measures» is not only the introduction of a ban on aggressive wars, but also the punishment of states planning, initiating and conducting aggressive war. However, the understanding of aggression as an international crime against the peace and security of humanity throughout the world has been and remains ambiguous.

One of the most topical issues of international criminal law is the study and analysis of the activities and practice of the International Criminal Court, i.e. an international body, with due regard for the prosecution of persons who plan, initiate and wage a war of aggression and punish them.

Keywords: crime, punishment, aggression, aggressor state, the International Criminal Court, international law.

An aggressor state is a term used to describe a state that actively engages in armed conflict or aggressively violates international law by invading or occupying another territory. The aggressor state usually violates the sovereignty of other states by using military force or the threat of force.

The term "aggressor state" has an international legal basis and is used in the Convention on the Prevention of Crimes against the Peace and Security of Mankind, adopted by the UN General Assembly in 1974. The Convention defines an aggressor state as a state that engages in armed aggression against another state or armed invasion of its territory.

The aggressor state must be subjected to international sanctions and condemned by the international community for its actions. International organizations such as the United Nations could adopt resolutions condemning an aggressor state and calling on it to stop aggression and return to the peaceful settlement of disputes.

The aggressor state may have various motives for its aggression. It can be the pursuit of territorial expansion, control over resources, or political influence over other regions. In some cases, the aggressor state may have claims in certain territories, and hostilities are used to carry out those claims.

Under international law, the violation of the territorial integrity of another state was considered illegal and contrary to the principles of respect for the sovereignty and independence of states. Aggressor states were often subjected to international sanctions, diplomatic isolation or even military action by other states.

Some examples of aggressor states:

1. Nazi Germany (1939-1945): In World War II, Germany, under Adolf Hitler, invaded Poland, thus starting a conflict that led to a major war in Europe and elsewhere;

2. Iraq (1990-1991): Iraq, under the leadership of Saddam Hussein, occupied Kuwait in 1990, leading to the Persian War (1990-1991) and the "Desert Storm" military operation led by an international coalition including the US and other countries;

3. Russian Federation (2008, 2014-present): Russia invaded Georgia in 2008, conducting an operation in South Ossetia and Abkhazia. In 2014, Russia annexed Crimea and supported pro-Russian separatist movements in eastern Ukraine;

4. Syria (since 2011): The conflict in Syria began in 2011 and has since degenerated into a civil war. In the course of this war, Syrian Government forces, as well as various factions and foreign actors, committed aggressive actions against the opposition and the civilian population.

5. The Republic of Armenia in the 1990s. The occupation of Nagorny Karabakh and surrounding territories, including seven Azerbaijani districts, which it controlled until 2020. As a result of the occupation of those territories, hundreds of thousands of Azerbaijanis had to leave their homes and become internal refugees. The international community, including the United Nations, had condemned the occupation of those territories and had called for their liberation. Several resolutions were adopted by the UN Security Council demanding the withdrawal of Armenian armed forces from the occupied territories. However, the Karabakh conflict was finally resolved by the Republic of Azerbaijan in 2020 as a result of 44 days of war.

In each of these cases, states used military force or carried out aggressive actions in violation of international law and the sovereignty of other states. This has had serious geopolitical consequences and has often required international intervention to restore peace and stability.

It is important to note that the use of the term "aggressor state" can be politically subjective and give rise

to debate depending on the specific situation and the views of different parties.

Punishment of the aggressor state could be carried out in various ways, including diplomatic, economic and legal measures. Here are some examples:

a) diplomatic pressure: The international community can condemn the aggressor and isolate it diplomatically. This may include the expression of condolences and support for affected countries, the adoption of resolutions or declarations, and sanctions at the international level.

b) economic sanctions: aggressor states may be subject to economic sanctions, which may include restrictions on trade, investment and financial transactions. This could seriously affect the economy and resources of the aggressor and stimulate a change in its policies.

c) military intervention: in certain cases, if the aggressor state poses a direct threat to peace and security, other states or international organizations may take military intervention measures to stop the aggression and restore peace.

d) international courts: if there are grounds for charging an aggressor state with crimes against humanity or a violation of international law, international courts such as the International Criminal Court (ICC) or the United Nations International Court of Justice, they can act and hold the aggressor accountable.

It is important to note that the choice and application of these measures depend on the political context, the strength and capacity of the international community and the will and consent of states parties. Each case of aggression required individual analysis and international cooperation to take appropriate measures within the framework of international law.

The last paragraph, relating to international courts, provided for the possibility of holding the aggressor state accountable for crimes against humanity or violations of international law. Some of the most prominent international courts that can try such cases include the International Criminal Court and the United Nations International Court of Justice.

The International Criminal Court is an independent international body established by the Rome Statute in 1998. It is competent to try crimes against humanity, war crimes and genocide. However, the ICC has jurisdiction only over states that have become members of the ICC, or in the event that a case has been referred to the ICC by the UN Security Council.

If the aggressor state is tried before international courts, the court will examine the arguments and evidence presented to determine whether international norms have been violated and whether crimes have been committed. As a result, the court may issue a decision that includes determining the responsibility of the aggressor, imposing sanctions or seeking compensation for the affected countries.

It is important to note, however, that not all states recognize the jurisdiction and authority of international courts. In some cases, aggressor states may refuse to cooperate with international courts or not recognize their competence. This may create obstacles to the trial and prosecution of the aggressor.

If the aggressor state did not cooperate with the international court or refused to implement its decisions, the international community could take additional measures, such as tightening economic sanctions or referring it to the United Nations Security Council. The United Nations Security Council, as the principal organ of the United Nations, may adopt a resolution requiring the aggressor state to respect international law and cease its aggressive actions. In some cases, the UN Security Council may even use coercive measures, including the use of force to end aggression.

It is important to note that international law and its courts are not always unequivocally applied and political circumstances may affect their effectiveness and implementation. Bringing the aggressor state to justice requires strong international support, cooperation and agreement among states to ensure justice and prevent the recurrence of aggression.

The final punishment of the aggressor state and its leaders may depend on the outcome of the proceedings and the decisions taken. This may include criminal prosecution of those responsible, payment of compensation and reparation, and political or diplomatic sanctions aimed at preventing the recurrence of aggression.

The question of the effectiveness of the International Criminal Court in punishing the aggressor state was complex and gave rise to divergent views. It is important to understand that the ICC has limited jurisdiction and cannot prosecute states themselves, but only individuals.

The ICC may try crimes against humanity, war crimes and genocide if the case has been referred to the ICC by the UN Security Council or if a state has become a member of the ICC and has accepted the jurisdiction of the court. However, it may be rare for an aggressor state to voluntarily agree to be tried or for a case to be referred to the ICC by the UN Security Council.

Moreover, the possibility of bringing the aggressor state to justice through the ICC could face political obstacles. Some states, especially those facing allegations, may refuse to cooperate with the ICC or not recognize its competence. This may create difficulties in gathering evidence and bringing those responsible to trial.

Despite these limitations, the ICC does play an important role in bringing to justice individuals who have committed crimes against humanity and war crimes. It strengthens international law and signals that violations of international norms will not go unpunished. The ICC can also contribute to reparation, justice and rehabilitation for victims.

It should be noted, however, that the effectiveness of the ICC in punishing the aggressor state depends on the political support and cooperation of states, as well as on the will of the international community to accept and support its decisions. This is a complex and multifaceted process that requires strong political and international assistance to ensure justice and punishment of the aggressor State. Ultimately, the effectiveness of the ICC in punishing an aggressor state depends on several factors, including:

1. Political will: Strong political support from Member States for the ICC and the international community as a whole is essential to the effectiveness of the ICC. If states unanimously condemn the aggressor and seek justice, it can create pressure and encourage cooperation with the ICC.

2. International cooperation: The cooperation of states in providing information, arresting suspects and transferring evidence to the ICC is crucial for the successful prosecution of the case and the prosecution of the aggressor state. If states cooperate and comply with their obligations to cooperate with the ICC, this can enhance its effectiveness.

3. International support: Broad international support in the form of sanctions, political pressure and public condemnation can also influence the aggressor state and its decision to cooperate with the ICC. This can help to create the conditions necessary for trial and prosecution.

4. Fairness and Trust: In order to effectively punish the aggressor state, judicial proceedings must be fair, independent and transparent. This is important to maintain the confidence of States Parties and the international community as a whole.

5. International solidarity: Solidarity and unity among states, especially those that are victims of aggression, are important. When the international community acts as one force, it can influence the aggressor state and create the conditions for punishment.

6. Length of proceedings: The trial before the ICC can be long and complex. Holding an aggressor state accountable can take a long time and requires patience and restraint. In this context, it is important to maintain a long-term strategy and not to lose international support and attention to the situation.

7. Implementation: Even if the ICC has handed down a punitive order, its implementation may face difficulties. The aggressor state may oppose the enforcement of decisions, and the international community may face restrictions in the application of sanctions or other measures to ensure the enforcement of the decision.

Overall, the effectiveness of the ICC in punishing the aggressor state depends on a complex interaction of political, legal and practical factors. It is an instrument of international justice and can contribute to justice and the principles of international law. However, without broad international support, political will and the cooperation of states, achieving the punishment of an aggressor state can be a difficult task.

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